

History of Theatre, Historiography and Humanities

The Principles of Deconstruction and Hermeneutics in Theatre: A Critical Inquiry into
Philosophical Paradigms and Performance Interpretation

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the theoretical intersection between deconstruction and hermeneutics within the field of theatre research, focusing on the interpretive potential these paradigms offer for performance analysis. Through an in-depth examination of Ingmar Bergman's staging of Yukio Mishima's *Madame de Sade*, the article applies Jacques Derrida's deconstructive methodology alongside hermeneutic perspectives informed by Freddie Rokem and Thomas Postlewait. The discussion addresses the dialectic between text and performance, the construction and deconstruction of meaning, and the historiographical implications of directorial interpretation. Additionally, the analysis considers Jerzy Grotowski's "poor theatre" as a counterpoint, revealing how differing artistic philosophies engage with narrative, representation, and the audience's interpretive agency.

Keywords: deconstruction; hermeneutics; theatre historiography; Bergman; Mishima; dramaturgy; performance theory; interpretation

INTRODUCTION

This paper discusses the potential application of deconstruction, appropriation, narrativity, and hermeneutics as historiographical methods in the production of Mishima's (Yukio Mishima) play, *Madamme de Sade*, directed by Ingmar Bergman, in connection with the "Grotowsky method" and historiographical essays written by Freddie Rokem and Thomas Postlewait.

Taking into consideration that Derrida (Jacques Derrida), on many occasions, rejected the idea of deconstruction as a new method of reading and interpretation, or its understanding,¹ the context of Rokem's (Freddie Rokem) *Ingmar Bergman's Aesthetics of Hiding* will be elaborated further on.

*Deconstruction takes place; it is an event that does not await the deliberation, consciousness, or organisation of a subject, or even of modernity.*²

According to Derrida, deconstruction is powered by the text it accesses, trying not to enter anything that its existing organisation has, in one way or another, but highlighted or hinted at by it already. At the same time, he acknowledged that certain elements, rules, and procedures of reading and interpretation can be repeated and transmitted from one text to another. Also, it repeats the production of logocentric relationships, such as those between internal and external, or between the centre and the margin. This duality is then examined as the difference between the immanent³ and transcendent criticism.⁴

¹ See: Derrida 1981A,128; Derrida 1997A, 27; Derrida, Jacques.2004. *Dissemination..* Trans. Johnson, Barbara. New York: Continuum, p. 9-16.

² See: Derrida, Jacques. 1985. "Letter to a Japanese Friend" in Derrida and Difference, ed. Wood & Bernasconi, Warwick: Parousia Press 1985, p. 1-5.

³ Immanent critique as a method of discussing culture regarding contradictions we are finding in society and systems: *An immanent critique of society is a critique which derives the standards it employs from the object criticised, that is, the society in question, rather than approaching that society with independently justified standards.* See Titus,Stahl (2013): "What is Immanent Critique?", SSRN Working Papers, URL:<http://ssrn.com/abstract=2357957>, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.2357957, retrieved 17.11.'19. at 7:47 pm

⁴ *For Marx, the value of an immanent approach to criticism lies in its objective or scientific character. By appealing to historically existing norms, immanent critique avoids the caprice and moralistic fault-finding typical of transcendent or utopian forms of criticism-those which invoke criteria lacking intrinsic connection to the real.* See Buchwalter, Andrew. (1987). *Hegel, Adorno and The Concept of Transcendent Critique. Philosophy & Social Criticism*, 12(4), 297-328. <https://doi.org/10.1177/019145378701200402> , retrieved 17.11.'19. at 4:35 pm

Derrida pointed out that the two approach each other and are intertwined. This takes place in a space that is neither completely inside nor quite beyond the meaningful units they affect, the margin. Ultimately, all of these complex events serve as a blueprint for a general deconstruction strategy.

In the context of appropriation regarding the Rokem's essay forementioned, as a term of art criticism, appropriation is used for description of creative procedures he has found in the Bergman's directing process, describing the photograph on the programme for the production of *Madame de Sade*: "This hand Bergman's own, is perhaps the hand of creation, calling up associations of the famous painting by Michelangelo. However, the photograph does not reveal the object of creation for that painting. Adam."⁵ (Rokem 1999: 81).

Defining an appropriation as a transmitter of the elements from one system of notion, or artistic discourse, the meaning of appropriation is considered as an aspect of idea, language, theme, genre, media, culture, and the aspect of usage of elements from other works in the process of creating an artwork. In postmodern discourse, the creative process is based on the appropriation of paintings, objects, videography, photography, etc. However, appropriation in art is a recycling event. The artist takes some elements, methods, formulas, styles and techniques, but the authenticity of each artwork is in the personal touch of the artist. An appropriation cannot destroy the originality of the artwork. In this term, the appropriation plays the role of initial impulse and inspiration.

Considering Bergman as one of the pioneer directors of postmodern theatre, his work can be analysed from a hermeneutic perspective. As the initial hypothesis for hermeneutic discussion of theatre that nothing in the theatre does not imply itself and it is all a matter of interpretation, Rokem gives, in the essay mentioned above, an introduction to Bergman's persona complexity, slightly immersing us into the world of *apperception and non-appereception*. These enigmatic and behavioural theatre games are longing for a deeper explanation hereinafter.

⁵ Describing the photograph on the programme of Bergman's production of Mishima's play *Madame de Sade*, premiered in the Royal Dramatic Theatre in Stockholm in 1989, Rokem actually does not clearly use the definition of appropriation, but rather points to the application of this technique and uses his estimation triggered by archived materials, comparing with the famous fresco painting of Michelangelo *The Creation of Adam*, a part of the Sistine Chapel's ceiling.

ILLUSION, HIDING AND BRUTALITY IN *MADAME DE SADE* – Freddie Rokem’s deconstruction of Ingmar Bergman’s production in 1989 at *The Royal Dramatic Theatre* in Stockholm

Yukio Mishima based the drama *Madame de Sade* (written in 1965) on a book by Shibusawa Tatsuhiko, originally titled *Sado kōshaku no shōgai* (The Life of Marquis de Sade).⁶ The plot of the drama takes place before and after the French Revolution. This affects Marquis de Sade’s wife, her family, acquaintances, and how the story goes its course; we can notice that appearances of the characters are actually all females. In the performance of Bergman’s production six actresses took their roles: Renee, the wife of the Marquis de Sade (Stina Ekbald); her sister Anne (Marie Richardson); Madame de Montreuil, the mother of Renee and Anne (Anita Björk); her servant Charlotta (Helena Brodin); and two acquaintances – the Countess du Saint Fond (Agneta Ekmanner) and the Baroness de Simaine (Margaretha Byström).⁷ Madame de Montreuil and her two daughters are historical figures. Mishima invents other female characters.

The setting of the play is in a sophisticated Parisian salon, and this is a venue of three acts, three meetings: the first act in 1772, the second act in 1778 and the third act in 1790.

“Mishima cherished the richness of cultural tradition, Japanese as well as European. In this sense, he was a neoclassicist. In *The Sound of Waves* (Shiosai, 1954, tr. 1958), he drew on the Greek story of Daphnis and Chloe to portray modern, idyllic love. Besides employing Noh and Kabuki patterns in his play writing, he was an ardent student of Euripides and his psychology of tragedy, and of the French classics.” (Melanowicz 1992: 8).

⁶ Shibusawa Tatsuhiko (1928-1987), French scholar, writer, translator of de Sade and Cocteau, author of *Sado Koshaku no Shogai* (The Life of Marquis de Sade, 1964). See Melanowicz, Mikolaj. 1992. “The Power of Illusion”. *Japan Review* no.3: 1-13, p.8

⁷ See Rokem, Freddie. 1999. “Historiography, Biography and Theatrical Representation. Ingmar Bergman’s Aesthetic of Hiding.” In *Nordic Theatre Studies*, vol.12, p.82.

This may be the key to his success in Japan, bringing the cultural fusion of the East and the West, despite the credit not going to the neoclassical style.⁸

The collection of twenty essays *Appreciations of Japanese Culture*, written by Donald Keen, illuminates Japanese tradition from the aspects of Japanese literature regarding boundaries of individualism, avoidance of emotional expression, appreciation of teamwork, religious and political backgrounds, as well as history. As a translator of Mishima's *Madame de Sade*, Keene is deeply connected with Mishima's work and personality. A postscript to the American edition of Donald Keene's translation of *Madame de Sade* written by Mishima might explain his longing to define a mystery of human psyche by creating an illusion as a survival tool for human's mental wellbeing and happiness: "Reading *The Life of the Marquis de Sade* by Tatsuhiko Shibusawa I was most intrigued as a writer, by the riddle of why the Marquise de Sade should have left him [her husband] the moment that he was at last free. I was sure that something highly incomprehensible, yet highly truthful, about human nature lay behind this riddle."⁹

"Donatien Alphonse Francois, Comte de Sade (b. 1740, Paris; d. 1814, Charenton, near Paris) in 1763 married the daughter of a high-ranking bourgeois family, the Montreuil. By her, he had two sons and one daughter. In the very first months of his marriage, he began an affair with an actress, and then he invited prostitutes to his "little house" at Arcueil. For various sexual abuses, he was imprisoned (in the fortress of Vincennes). After a new public scandal, he was sentenced to the fortress near Lyon for a second time. After his release and retirement to his chateau of La Coste, he committed new sexual excesses and fled to the estates of the King of Sardinia, where he was again arrested. After escaping from the fortress of Miolans, Sade rejoined his wife, who from that time became his accomplice and shared his pleasures. Following new incidents and scandals, the Marquis was arrested in Paris and sent to Vincennes in 1777, where he attempted to incite the other prisoners to revolt. Visits from his wife were banned due to his jealous fit. After that, the Marquise

⁸ *The Japanese audience would rather feel discouraged by the picture of a sophisticated salon, distant from its stylishly dressed women. One might say that these are not flesh-and-blood women but just rococo dresses cast in the roles of advocates of law and morals, religion, bodily desires, womanly sincerity and absence of rules and the people embodied in the maid costume. See: Melanowicz, Mikolaj. 1992. "The Power of Illusion". Japan Review no.3: 1-13, p.8-9*

⁹ See: Melanowicz, Mikolaj. 1992. "The Power of Illusion". *Japan Review* no.3: 1-13, p.31

retired to a convent. In 1784, he was transferred to the Bastille in Paris. At the beginning of the Revolution, he was once again moved to the insane asylum at Charenton, from which he was released shortly thereafter.

His new role started as an activist of the revolution and a writer. Separated from his wife, he lived with a young widowed actress while he wrote his novels *Justine, ou les malheurs de la vertu* and *Juliette*.” (Melanowicz 1992: 31).

In the documentary film (1985) *The Strange Case of Yukio Mishima*, Mishima himself explains his way of seeing and perceiving the brutal side of human nature, which is apparently his reflection on female characters in this drama play:

“ You can easily find two contradictory characteristics of Japanese characters. One is elegance, and the other is brutality, but these two characteristics are sometimes very tightly combined, and I think our brutality comes from our emotions. It is never recognised or systematised like nazi’s brutality. I think that brutality might come from our feminine aspect, and elegance comes from our nervous side. Sometimes we are too sensitive to definition, or elegance, or sense of beauty on the aesthetic side, and sometimes we are tired of it. We need, sometimes, an explosion to make us free from it.”¹⁰

This claim explains his vision of how to see male complex psychology through women’s eyes. However, the Marquis himself doesn’t enter the stage, although he is the object and the main subject of the lives of all women on the stage. Rokem compares this experience-

¹⁰ See: *The Strange Case of Yukio Mishima* (1985). BBC, Arena documentary. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ctufj50w9a0> retrieved 16.11.’19. at 11:35 “A fascinating documentary about the famous Japanese Writer and Nationalist Yukio Mishima. This BBC-produced documentary about Yukio Mishima highlights the many known major aspects of his life and personality. Mishima was a pen name he adopted en route to his chosen life as a writer. He eventually became recognised as one of Japan’s most prolific post-World War II writers, producing stories, plays and novels. He became tortured by his bisexuality/homosexuality and shyness around people as a young man. Both of these played a role in his work, as did many other eventful occurrences throughout his life. Mishima had an admirable dedication to the forgotten samurai way of life and ideals, which later turned into an unhealthy obsession, culminating in the storming of a general’s garrison on November 25, 1970. It was Mishima’s way of combining beauty, art, and action; ultimately, the garrison forced to assemble and listen to his speech on that day rejected him. Mishima gave his life for his ideals, however misguided and twisted one might think him to be. His literary output of 40 novels, 18 plays (both for Noh and Kabuki theatre), 20 books of short stories, 20 books of essays, and a film remains a testament to his talent despite his simultaneous tendency, at times, to be commercial, controversial, and unconventional.”

non-appearence game, in a deconstructive essay, as a director's physical absence from his own work, because of the previously explained purpose of the image on the programme, Bergman's own hand, which reinforces such an interpretation.¹¹ The main character does not enter the stage at all during the whole performance. At this point, Rokem makes a comparison with Beckett's *Waiting for Godot*: " [...] this is no doubt a variation of the theological thematics of Beckett's *Waiting for Godot*, where Godot does not appear at the end of both acts of the play."

In fact, Marquis does not appear physically in the play, but female characters blocked his reappearance using their brutal aspect of their feminine side. It is a punishment for the male, and it is no longer possible to destroy the illusion of a peaceful world where Renee lives. This is how female lives were transformed under the influence of the thoughts and deeds in his absence. In Melanowitz's textual deconstruction, the illusion of Renee is described as a rejection of the good of fiction of illusion, or the image of the man she has loved a long time ago:

"Madame de Sade (Renee) rejected reality-her own real husband, in his shabby state-and chose the fiction of illusion, the image of the man she had known long before, which she perceived as reality. She rejected the shadow of Alphonse de Sade waiting outside the door and decided to take along only a source of *the light* she believed he was. So the imaginary de Sade, which Renee is going to take along to a nunnery, is more real and important to her than the older man outside her chambers. The latter seems to be the opposite of the de Sade she loved; therefore, Renee cannot accept him if she is supposed to remain true to her own self."(Melanowitz 1992: 10).

Mishima also claims that the reason for writing this play, a fusion of Japanese narrative and European culture, was that he wanted to explore the reason for this non-appearance. The moment when she, Renee, refuses to see her husband, the Marquis de Sade, in the last scene of the play (Rokem 1999: 83). In the programme of Bergman's production, his postscript is published:

¹¹ See: Rokem, Freddie. 1999. "Historiography, Biography and Theatrical Representation. Ingmar Bergman's Aesthetic of Hiding." In *Nordic Theatre Studies*, vol.12, p.82.

“When I read *The Life of the Marquis de Sade* by Tatsuhiro Shibusawa, I was captivated, as a writer, by the enigmatic fact that Madame de Sade, after having shown such inviolable loyalty to her husband during his long years of imprisonment, deserted him the moment he was finally released. This riddle served as the point of departure for my drama, which is an attempt to give it a logical solution. I realised that behind this riddle, it is possible to find something complicated to understand, but which at the same time is very true about human nature. I wanted to explore de Sade and keep the whole thing within this frame of reference. This play can thus be characterised as de Sade seen by women’s eyes.”¹²

Bergman’s presentation of de Sade is an enigmatic play, a reflection of himself, perhaps, or the mysterious storyteller. Rokem sees his hiding as a paravane, or covered chauvinism and voyeurism:

“The female characters present on the stage reject the reappearance of de Sade and his penetration of the female space that the play/performance has established. And paradoxically, at the same time, the play expresses Mishima’s fascination with the riddle of femininity, rejecting the entry of the male. When this play is transformed into a performance, it reproduces this masculine desire through the director’s vision, controlling the female actresses on the stage playing the roles in Mishima’s play. Bergman directing Mishima thus establishes a meta-theatrical correspondence which can give us an insight into the art of directing itself, as the art of absent presences where the director is at the same time creator and spectator.”¹³

Related to this observation, Rokem analyses Charlotte, a servant, as a representation of Bergman’s hand in the performance:

“[...] despite her minor role, she is present on the stage throughout virtually the whole performance, sometimes almost hiding behind the columns in the set, sometimes revealing her presence more openly. However, she is always carefully watching what the other characters are

¹² Rokem’s translation of the programme for *Madame de Sade*, Kungliga Dramatiska Teatern, 1989. In Rokem, Freddie. 1999. “Historiography, Biography and Theatrical Representation. Ingmar Bergman’s Aesthetic of Hiding.” In *Nordic Theatre Studies*, vol.12, p.83 and 93.

¹³ Ibid.

saying and doing. Charlotte is witnessing the gradual disintegration of the aristocratic society which she has been serving. While Bergman is secretly watching the action from his hidden position behind the stage, Charlotte is a liminal figure situated inside the border of the stage [...].”¹⁴

Rokem’s *Ingmar Bergman’s Aesthetic of Hiding* is a presentation that is situated at the intersection of verbal and visual systems in writing and the image as a letter. We find the analogy of pictorial and textual. First, he locates a network of different speaking productions, i.e. discourse, which appear in the format of an image. Secondly, he shows how different meanings are constituted and transformed, producing differences in the context of structural and temporal relations.

As a practical procedure of performing an artistic piece, deconstruction has a poetic and interventional character. Deconstruction does not seek to resolve or to isolate the ideal representation, e.g. film, performance, text, music, photograph, painting, but rather indicates that different practices of artistic expression acquire their meaning in relation to other historical or current models.

Regarding Rokem’s aforementioned essay, his text can be classified under the term deconstruction because it serves not only to introduce new knowledge about the order and its decomposition or reconstruction, but also, performatively and interventionally, demonstrates a way of integrating and disintegrating the model of Western metaphysics.

¹⁴ Ibid. p.92

META-THEATRE, NARRATIVE AND HERMENEUTICS - Grotowsky and Postlewait's philosophical reading and understanding

A theatrical or performance work presents certain theoretical and ideological aspects. Still, through its structure of labelling, it also reveals how an event, a situation, or a performance creates space for theory and ideology. Theatre as a spiritual and artistic space, in which the art of theatre is explored in terms of acting, dancing, directing, scenography, meditation and rituals, is characteristic of modernism and avant-garde. In the case of neovanguard and postvanguard, the notion of the theatrical laboratory was introduced by Jerzy Grotowski in the late 1950s until the early 1970s.¹⁵ His theatrical space is clear, liberated from literature, music and visual arts, the concept of a “poor theatre”, the opposition to the total theatre. His theatrical space is transformed into a theatre as an institution of spectacle.

“ There is a name in the theatre of our time that is more prestigious than any other. It is perhaps more of an incantation than a name, and even more than an incantation, a magic formula. It is the words of *Jerzy Grotowski*, the name of the founder and director of The Polish Laboratory Theatre of Wroclaw.” (*John Simon*).¹⁶

We can also notice that his method goes over barriers and moves from the theatre as an institution to the theatre as a phenomenon. Theatrical work in this concept catalyses the verification of the spiritual and physical presence of participants throughout the entire process of creating theatre art.

The development of Grotowski's work led to the concept of theatre practice as a meta research of nature and the idea of theatre as an art and social practice – metatheater. In practice, it has been represented during the '60s of the 20th Century in *The Living Theatre* and *Odin Theatre* by rethinking the avant-garde tradition regarding a formal physical, spatial and temporal exploration of discursive and non-discursive theatre, late neoavantgarde and early postavantgarde. Also, the theoretical and political formulation of the nature of the theatrical experiment (the set-guard

¹⁵ “Jerzy Grotowski (1933–1999), Polish theatre director, cultural practitioner and thinker, researcher of human behaviour under *meta-daily conditions*.” 50th Anniversary of the founding of the Laboratory Theatre, 2009 pdf.

¹⁶ Simon, John. "Grotowski's Grotesqueries." *The Hudson Review* 23, no. 3 (1970): 510-21

phase at the turn of the 60s in 70s; the politicisation of *The Living Theatre* and the equalisation of domains of action are characteristic theatrical and political domains in the physical and ambient event). However, we find a critique and deconstruction of exclusive and autonomous modernity - a return to the ritualistic, shamanistic interruption of the fundamental theatrical relationship between actor and audience. An exploration of the ethno-theatre and non-European ritual, dance and theatrical ritual-magic systems, thereby establishing the polyzine, pluralistic and eclectic ritual of rituals inherent in postmodern, nomadic or trans-movement from metatheatre to pararitual archetypal act.¹⁷

However, the term “metatheatre”, in this context, demands a clear clarification. Metatheatre and meta-performance are behavioural events in space and time that are not only aimed at achieving an artistic or aesthetic effect, but also at discussing the nature of autoreflexivity through pedagogy, theory, the meaning of theatre, and its concepts, as well as the principles of usage for theatre art.

Here I would like to point out on Lacan’s (Jacques Lacan) famous hypothesis that there is no such thing as a metalanguage.¹⁸ But does it mean in the context of the theatre? His claim is essential for postmodern and post-avant-garde theatre and performance art. Theoretical psychoanalysis states that “There is no metalanguage”, but it does not deny the existence of expressions, examples and patterns of metalanguage. It shows that metalanguage does not have the universal meaning or legitimacy of privileged language. In every metalanguage, at one of its instances of appearance and presentation, the signifier penetrates, introducing the dialectic of subjectivity, including cases of paradox, inconsistency, and so on. The metatheater does behave analogously to the psychoanalytic model.

¹⁷ See: Eugenio Barba “Odin Teatret” <https://odinteatret.dk/about-us/eugenio-barba/> ; <http://old.odinteatret.dk/research/ista/theatre-anthropology.aspx> retrieved 21.11.’19. at 19:02 and Richard Schechner “Performance Theory” <http://www.icosilune.com/2009/01/richard-schechner-performance-theory/> retrieved 21.11.’19. at 19:05

¹⁸ Jacques Lacan, a French psychoanalyst (1901-1981), “Jacques [Lacan](#) took up the concept of metalanguage developed in twentieth-century logic by Alfred Tarski and Bertrand [Russell](#).” See: <http://cahiers.kingston.ac.uk/concepts/metalanguage.html> and <https://www.iep.utm.edu/lacweb/> retrieved 21.11. ’19. at 20:02

Considering historical structures in the long term (*longue durée*) as a structuralistic idea and conceptually operates as a formal idea of historical knowledge, or constitutive category regarding ordering a history, often serves a hermeneutical function (Postlewait 1992: 360). Hermeneutical function can be seen through the concept of Rankean or Hegelian history :

“The hermeneutic method as conceived by Ranke was inseparable from certain basic philosophic assumptions. What made historical knowledge possible for Ranke, as it did for the German tradition of hermeneutics for over a century from Wilhelm von Humboldt and Friedrich Schleiermacher to J. G. Droysen, Wilhelm Dilthey, and Friedrich Meinecke, was the notion that history was the realm of "spirit," but of spirit conceived very differently from the way it was understood in Hegel's philosophy. If Hegel had stressed the unity of world history and had seen in history a process in which spirit through continuous self-negation translated itself into increasingly rational institutions, the hermeneutic tradition ... stressed that spirit manifested itself in individualised forms. History was made up of "individualities," each possessing its internal structure and a meaning and purpose unique to it alone. Not only persons possessed the qualities of individuality, but in an even more profound sense so did the great collective bodies which had grown in the course of history, states, nations, cultures, mankind.”¹⁹

However, the structuralist formulations of reconstructing a “collectivity” in the past become the collective mentality of the historian. Regarding this, Postlewait says:

“So, the idea of *longue duree*- like other popular concepts such as mentalite, episteme, zeitgeist, gestalt, paradigm, discourse, ideology, hegemony, civilising process, discursive formations- serves as an interpretive model for identifying and explaining historical conditions, social practices, and epochs. More to the point, a narrative of social thought, behaviour, power, and control emerges from these concepts. Of course, there are numerous differences in interpretive meaning between concepts such as Ranke's historical spirit of power, Marx's ideology, Burckhardt's culture, Weber's Protestant ethic, Talcott Parsons' functionalism, Jacques Le Goff's mentalité, Jurgen Habermas's modernity, and Michel Foucault's discursive formations.

¹⁹ See: Postlewait, Thomas. 1992. “History, Hermeneutics, and Narrativity.” In *Critical Theory and Performance*. p.358

But in terms of interpretive strategy, a process of constituting and framing history by means of ideas that function as models of explanation, these concepts reveal striking similarities. Moreover, each concept produces a narrative, an organised representation (mimesis) and emplotment (mythos) of how and why events and actions occur. That is the whole point.”²⁰

According to Gadamer (Hans-Georg Gadamer), the task of philosophical hermeneutics is to expose the hermeneutical dimension to its full extent and to emphasise its fundamental meaning for our whole understanding of the world in all its forms.²¹ That means that one is capable of understanding surroundings, from interpersonal communication to social manipulation, from the experience of the individual in society, as well as the experience he has gained about himself. Additionally, to understand the tradition of production, one must consider the interplay between religion and law, art and philosophy, and the liberating and reflexive energy of revolutionary consciousness. Hermeneutics is a skill in understanding and interpreting a text. Hermeneutics in theatre and the hermeneutics of theatre refer to the skill of understanding and interpreting a dramatic text and a theatrical object, being, situation, or event as a text.

“In the title of his article, *History, Hermeneutics, and Narrativity*, Thomas Postlewait frames the word *hermeneutics* with *history* on one side and *narrativity* on the other. Postlewait conceives hermeneutics as Hans-Gregor Gadamer does (following Heidegger) as the phenomenology of reading. Gadamer’s account of the hermeneutic circle includes the idea of *fore-structure understanding*, an acknowledgement that readers come to text with what reader-response theorists have called *a horizon of expectation* which prepares and shapes their reception of the work.” (Reinelt/Roach 2005: 354-355).

The notion of meaning in theatre formally encompasses the skeleton of what necessarily belongs to something which is articulating an understandable presentation on stage. The hermeneutical understanding of theatre as a text moves in a logically impermissible, but closed and fruitful, hermeneutic circle that, as the fundamental law of knowledge, should determine each hermeneutic reflection. And how we perceive one theatrical event, individually, can be

²⁰ See: Postlewait, Thomas. 1992. “History, Hermeneutics, and Narrativity.” In *Critical Theory and Performance*. p.361

²¹ See: <https://www.iep.utm.edu/gadamer/> retrieved 21.11.’19. at 21:52

understood only based on the proper entirety, which includes theater history, theater paradigm, theatrical context, the relation of one theatre event with another theatre event, but the entirety of the theatre can be understood and revised based on psychoanalytical side, because the signifier always penetrates signified (point de capture).

Once ontological characterisations of hermeneutics are seen through the prisms of a structuralist or a post-structuralist and their interpretations, they become topological characterisations. Therefore, the methodological context in depth Postlewait explains on the example of his essay:

“Hermeneutics, which I define broadly as the theory of interpretation, provides the basis for analysis in this essay but is not, I want to insist, an essential, foundational, or systematic method for discovering and expressing truth. Historical scholarship, though diligent in its search for what happened in the past, is not a discipline that discovers final truths. Its problems, as I conceive them, are primarily epistemological rather than ontological. Historical reports are representations, perhaps supreme fictions, of the past, but not incarnations. I thus wish to distinguish my use of the concept from that of the exegetical tradition that developed in hermeneutics as a means of bringing forth the buried, hidden, or secret meanings of sacred texts, a process of uncovering and revealing an ultimate truth.” (Postlewait 1992: 365).

We can notice a close connection between Postlewait’s definition and Gadamer’s thoughts in relation to defining hermeneutics. It must be defined in a way that takes into consideration the entire sphere of art, or, in this context, the entire sphere of theatre as an art form. If each text needs to be interpreted, then hermeneutics should also include an understanding of each work of art. That includes theatre, literature, visual and musical forms of art.

CONCLUSION

As mentioned earlier in the text, theatre work appears to the modern spectator as *a past horizon* which is longing to be linked to their own present understanding (presence and existence in the current “world of the theatre”). The relationship between theatre history, normative styles and current theatrical trends is not that simple to understand. It might be an essential determinant of interpretative pinpointing, description and exceeding the horizon of difficulty. In the methodological context characteristic of the hermeneutical approaches to theatre history, observing or reading a drama piece is based on recognising its place in the context of creation. Also, the context of a very creation must be considered globally. We must understand social, cultural, theoretical and artistic-theatrical relations as a whole, creating a wider picture of the world around us.

Performance, as a domain, exists only when it is performed. It necessarily requires the presence of others and an interpersonal relationship.

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